

RERAM

research to innovation in
resource efficiency

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Reality checks and benchmarking of raw material performance

Resource efficiency checks and trainings of
woodworking and furniture enterprises in
Austria, Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia

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1. Objectives

This deliverable is a final activity report of the RERAM project activities targeting woodworking enterprises in the ENP-EaP countries:

- Task 3.1: Technological guidance for resource efficiency and raw materials
- Task 3.2: Training, coaching and advisory services in environmental management
- Task 3.3: Reality check and benchmarking of raw material flows and performance

Task 3.1 main objective is to carry out a survey of existing guidelines and manuals on energy and resource efficiency in wood working sector. This task has been completed in period 1 and reported in the deliverable **D3.1** 'Metastudy'.

Task 3.2 main objectives are to conduct a series of interactive trainings/seminars for entrepreneurs to initiate and improve regional capacity and assistance to enterprises. Participants are trained on various aspects of integrated environmental protection.

Task 3.3 main objectives are to conduct real resource efficiency checks in companies in Austria, Ukraine, Moldova and Georgia. Participating companies are visited by the experts and analysed on potential savings. Based on the check, an implementation programme for improvement measures to the specific needs of the company is developed jointly.

This final report **D3.2** documents the complete work conducted during the periods 1 and 2 between 01/06/2014 to 31/05/2016. The dissemination level of the report is RESTRICTED, because it contains specific and confidential information of individual enterprises. The report **D3.3** is a shortened public summary version of this report.

2. Report on Activities and Achievements

2.1 Overview of conducted reality checks and trainings

The **RERAM Enterprise Efficiency Checks** offer a hands-on approach to raise awareness for Cleaner Production among companies. A team of trained experts visits a company to perform a quick 1-day check of the state of efficiency. A list of potentials and low investment solutions is identified and then discussed with the company manager (1st report), pointing out the **benefits of saved input resources** that can be valorised in the final product, which makes the company as a whole more efficient and competitive. Follow-up training and coaching is then offered to support the implementation of measures for improved material and energy use, safety and skills of workers.

In total, **19 companies** participated in the **RERAM enterprise reality checks** (Task 3.3, see Table 2), which were conducted in 4 different countries. The participating companies represented the whole wood value chain ranging from forest plant production, saw milling, solid wood panel production, furniture industry, carpentry, wood flooring industry, and windows and doors production.

Canvas of woodworking enterprises participating enterprise checks

Per each enterprise reality check, the team of experts collects a list of improvement options for resource and energy efficiency. The observations and suggested options are documented in an enterprise reality check report per each company. The Annex C of this report includes **17 detailed reality check reports** prepared by the RERAM experts. These reports were translated by the ENP partners into the national languages and then presented during follow-up meetings to the company director and/or technical manager to raise awareness and discuss the possibilities for the implementation of suitable measures in the company.

Furthermore, **5 joint company trainings** (1-3 day workshops) have been conducted in Ukraine, Georgia and Moldova (Task 3.2, see Annex B) as part of the enterprise check visits. During these workshops, which were held at the facilities of one of the participating companies, the Austrian experts and local advisors educated in the RERAM Train-the-Trainer programme (ToTs) trained and exchanged with company owners, production managers, and technical staff about the principles of cleaner production.

The training workshops for company managers and technical staff provided detailed information and examples on the following topics:

- Cleaner production vs. end of pipe
- Cleaner production options and strategies - company specific examples and solutions
- Material flow analysis - making wood and raw material flows visible
- Energy analysis and energy management
- Guidelines on energy efficiency in selected areas
- General input on pollution prevention & waste management
- Water management
- Waste management
- Initial auditing – preparing for the first company visit

The content of the training topics for ENP countries was chosen taking into considerations the outcome of the WP2 company assessment and the information provided by local experts from each country. The training materials are documented as part of the **RERAM Toolkit** (see **D4.3**) and have been published on the project website www.reram.eu.

The trainings for the Austrian companies were executed on as individual advisory sessions due to the advanced implementation of cleaner production principles in Austria. Cleaner production strategies are already part of company strategies due to legal requirements (national waste management schemes, EC directive on energy efficiency, worker's health and safety regulations).

In addition, high raw material prices and a competitive market environment have led to a high degree of automation and the implementation of management strategies on raw material efficiency across all value added stages. Therefore, the content of those individual trainings were based on the findings of the company checks and consultancy was given to managing directors, production managers and technical staff during a half-day session.

Table 1 List of woodworking companies participating in reality checks

No.	Company	Country	Products	Contact person	Check date
1	Mebli Stil Stryisky district, Lopatynsky Street 141, Ukraine http://mebli-stil.in.ua/	UA	Upholstered furniture	Mr. Volodymyr Turchyn (owner)	16/10/2014
2	K'Len 7, Lesia Ukrainka str, Ilnytsya, Irshava, Ukraine http://k-len.in.ua	UA	Woodworking, parquet	Mr. Vasyl Bizilya (director)	23/03/2015
3	Atlant Khust, Ukraine http://atlant.khust.com/features.html	UA	Woodworking (windows, doors, stairs, joinery)	Mr. Atlant (director)	26/03/2015
4	Gelika Chekhova str. 35A/2 Vynnytsya, Ukraine http://gelika.org/en	UA	Furniture	Mr. Shamansky (director)	05/04/2016
5	Goliat Vita Ltd Strada Lenin 11a, Comrat, Moldava http://goliat-vita.com.md	MD	Furniture	Mr. Anastasov Serghei (director)	05/05/2015
6	Mob-lumina Ltd, Mobilemn Ltd Comrat, Moldava	MD	Furniture	Mr. V. Zinaida (director), Mr. C. Iuri (director)	06/05/2015
7	Numina Ltd Chisinau, Moldava www.numina.md	MD	Furniture	Mr. Jeliuk Evghenii (director)	04/05/2015

No.	Company	Country	Products	Contact person	Check date
8	Orbeli JSC 5, Kindzmareuli str. 0145, Tbilisi, Georgia www.orbelihome.ge	GE	Furniture, windows, doors, stairs, joinery	Mr. B. Chkhaidze (director)	14/04/ 2015
9	Shno Ltd 5. Kindzmareuli str. Tbilisi, Georgia www.shno.ge	GE	Furniture, windows, doors, stairs, joinery	Mr. Givi Nioradze (director)	15/04/ 2015
10	Golden Hands Ltd 12 Chichinadze str. 0145, Georgia www.goldenhands.ge	GE	Furniture, windows, doors, stairs, joinery	A. Koptev (director)	15/04/ 2015
11	Tsunda Ltd 2. Chantladze str. 0109 Tbilisi, Georgia http://tsunda.ge/en/	GE	Furniture, windows, doors, stairs, joinery	A. Natenadze (director)	16/04/ 2015
12	Caucasus Road Project Ltd 44 Leselidze str., Tbilisi; 21 Nikea str., Kutaisi, GE www.crp.ge	GE	Secondary wood processing	Mr. Giori (director)	15/04/ 2015
13	Carpentry Tscheschner „Der Hobel“ Sackstraße 22, 8010 Graz www.derhobel.at	AT	Carpentry	Mr. Engelbert Tscheschner (owner)	04/12/ 2015
14	Carpentry Griessner www.tischlerei-griessner.at	AT	Carpentry	Ms. Cornelia Griessner (owner)	18/12/ 2015
15	Scheucher Parkett Zehensdorf 100 8092 Mettersdorf, Austria www.scheucher.at	AT	MULTIfloor Flooring industry	K. Scheucher (owner), K. Kaufmann	17/12/ 2015
16	LIECO Kalwang Kalwang, Austria www.lieco.at	AT	Forest seedling production	Mr. Bernd Iglar (operation manager)	19/11/ 2014
17	LIECO St. Martin Diesseits 73, 4973 St. Martin im Innkreis, Austria www.lieco.at	AT	Forest seedling production	Mr. Bernd Iglar (operation manager)	10/04/ 2015

No.	Company	Country	Products	Contact person	Check date
18	Jannach GmbH Thalheimerstraße 27 Thalheim, Austria www.jannach.com	AT	Sawmill & planing mill	Mr. Helmut Jannach (director)	09/04/2015
19	Prödl Carpentry 8324 Kirchberg / an der Raab 171, Austria www.proedl.at/en	AT	Carpentry/ Furniture production	Mr. Josef Prödl (director)	11/02/2015

Table 2 List of conducted enterprise reality checks and trainings

Date	City	Activity	Host	Participants
16/10/2014	Stryi, UA	Enterprise check MebliStil	UNFU	all consortium members (part of ToT training 1 st week)
11/02/2015	Kirchberg, AT	Enterprise visit and check Prödl	HCS	all consortium members (part of ToT training 2 nd week)
23-27/03/2015	Irshava/ Khust, MD	Enterprise checks K'Len, Atlant, 2 days training at K'Len	FORZA	HCS (C. Angerbauer, T. Dielacher, R. Oberwimmer), FORZA (Y. Derbal, L. Loyko, R. Ustych, N. Voloshyna) WPFC (V. Popovici), UNFU (I. Voytovych)
13-17/04/2015	Tbilisi, GE	Enterprise checks Orbeli, Shno, CRP, Golden Hands, Tsunda, 2 days training at Orbeli	AUG	HCS (C. Angerbauer, T. Dielacher, R. Oberwimmer), AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostharia)
09/04/, 30/09/2015	Thalheim, AT	Enterprise check and advisory session for Jannach	HCS	HCS (C. Angerbauer, T. Dielacher, R. Oberwimmer, M. Kolck)
19/11/, 10/04/, 28/09/2015	Kalwang/ St. Martin, AT	Enterprise check and advisory session for Lieco	HCS	HCS (C. Angerbauer, T. Dielacher, R. Oberwimmer, M. Kolck)
04-08/05/2015	Chisinau/ Comrat, MD	Checks Goliat-Vita, Numina, Mobilemn, Mob-Lumina, 2 days training at Goliat-Vita	AITT	HCS (C. Angerbauer, T. Dielacher), AITT (V. Iatchevici), WPFC (V. Popovici)

<i>Date</i>	<i>City</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Host</i>	<i>Participants</i>
04/12/2015	Graz, AT	Enterprise check and advisory session Tschechner	HCS	HCS (C. Angerbauer, R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt)
17/12/2015	Zehensdorf, AT	Enterprise check and advice for Scheucher	HCS	HCS (C. Angerbauer, R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt)
18/12/2015	Neumarkt, AT	Enterprise check and advice for Griessner	HCS	HCS (C. Angerbauer, R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt)
19-20/04/2016	Tbilisi, GE	1 day training for companies at RECC, enterprise re-visits of Shno, CRP, Golden Hands	RECC	HCS (C. Angerbauer, V. Jurniak, R. Oberwimmer), AUG (T. Kandelaki, M. Khostaria), RECC (S. Samkharadze, S. Akhobadze)
04-06/05/2016	Chisinau / Comrat, MD	1 day training for companies at AITT, re-visits of Goliat-Vita, Numina	AITT	HCS (C. Angerbauer, R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt), AITT (V. Iatchevici)
26-27/03/2016	Vinnytsya, UA	Enterprise check Gelika	FORZA	FORZA (Y. Derbal, N. Voloshyn), UNFU (I. Voytovych)

2.2 Results of checks and conclusions

The comparison of findings of RERAM company checks between Austria (benchmark reference country) and the three surveyed ENP-EaP countries (Georgia, Moldova, Ukraine) has led to **the following conclusions regarding the situation in the ENP-EaP countries:**

- Cleaner production approach was completely unknown in the ENP countries
- Very low environmental awareness in the wood working industry (and in general)
- Highly production (output) oriented with end-of-pipe thinking instead of preventive approaches
- Joint venture companies showed a higher level of production organization, better material handling and work place quality (observed only in Ukraine).
- Company managers are usually not educated in wood working, whereas company owners often showed a short-term profit oriented attitude (very few of the companies visited were more than 10 years on the market)
- Low managerial skills on work shop and production process organization
- Low skills and competences of the work force in wood working
- Lack of maintenance efforts and/or knowledge on maintenance
- Second hand equipment (but usually from well-known European and Asian manufacturers)

- Poor work place and air quality conditions (health, safety, significant risks of fire/explosion with two severe fire incidents in companies checked between 03/2015-05/2016)
- Low level of national regulations on waste (no requirements for waste separation systems, companies reported that costs for waste disposal are based on lump sums and not by volume) and work place safety
- Timber supply problems have often led to the substitution of domestic solid wood with imported wood panels (chipboard, MDF), import of veneers and semi-finished solid wood products (absence of modern sawmills with drying chambers)
- Auxiliary materials are often imported (paint, glue, textiles)
- Unsatisfying thermal and heating situation due to the use of outdated (yet cheap and abundant) work shop facilities from the communistic era
- No resource, waste or cost monitoring systems in place
- No energy monitoring in place

The company finding reports were presented and explained to company representatives, whereas the aggregated findings were discussed in panel sessions with a larger audience from business and administration. In addition, feedback, recommendations and training sessions on the most pressing topics related to raw material and resource efficiency were held.

Considering the difficult situation in ENP countries, the recommendations of the RERAM experts focused on **good housekeeping measures** (no-to-low cash investment with payoff period of less than 1 year) as the first steps towards the implementation of CP options. While most entrepreneurs easily understood the benefits of the CP approach for their company, there were concerns and uncertainties on where to start given the magnitude of potentials and options for improvements.

Therefore, the RERAM consortium put together a **low-level wood industry toolkit** (see **D4.3**) for entrepreneurs, local consultants and intermediaries to collect, analyze and monitor their raw material and resource consumption patterns along with information on the waste streams generated. Based on the analysis, the tools allow to identify the “low-hanging fruits” (large potentials with no investments) and to decide on targets for first CP projects.

In the following chapter, a short list of collected options for each checked enterprise are given to provide a readable, yet comprehensive overview of the findings in different countries and different areas of the wood value chains. With respect to the companies' participation in the audits, the consortium has observed that companies which have been either involved in international business or have already done first steps towards cleaner production were in particular interested in undergoing the company checks. As such it must be assumed, that the findings show a somewhat environmentally friendlier picture of the state-of-art of cleaner production in wood working industries.

2.3 CP options for improvement – overview

- **Awareness rising activities / trainings for employees** regarding efficiency. First step: motivate employees to switch off machines not in use
- **Improve waste management:** clean up scrap, storage of empty drums, waste segregation according to law, repeated trainings of employees
- **Improve dust collection:** empty dust collector sacks, link collector with motor switch, maintenance of exhaust system
- **Improve wood drying equipment:** change gaskets, install VFD, heat recuperation system, insulation of hot pipes
- **Improve recovery rate of wood:** implement indicators, improve cut-to-length, install crosscutting line, yield improvements
- **Improve handling of raw materials** and usable rest pieces, improve storage of wood material and saw dust (protection against rain/humidity)
- **Improve compressed air system:** leak testing and fixing, red-tag system, correct pressure adjustment
- **Improve spray painting:** new technologies, training of employees, proper usage of booth, sufficient lighting, no sanding close to painting
- **Improve maintenance of machines** to ensure quality and avoid considerable losses
- **Implement an indicator system** to monitor environmental performance
- **Improve lighting:** change to electronic ballast and LED lamps, use natural light, place in optimal height, motivate to switch off lights and clean lamps
- **Improve heating system and thermal insulation:** insulation of boiler and pipelines, seal gaps between doors and door frames, transparent sheets at doors, reflector behind radiator, insulation of pipes and valves
- **Improve storage of hazardous materials:** train employees in the classification and labelling of chemicals, seal ground in storage areas, close containers, implement secondary catchment, check the storage of hazardous materials regularly and dispose old/outdated paints
- **Improve risk management:** clear guidance, motivation of employees to wear Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)
- **Establish detailed machine lists:** power rating, age, operating hours, machine type and brand, maintenance intervals
- **Improve energy management:** frequent checks of the energy load profile to avoid expensive energy demand peaks; implement waste heat recovery solutions to save costs

2.4 CP options for improvement per company

This chapter is not included in the public summary report version because it contains company-specific information.

2.5 Study trip of Ukrainian wood enterprises to Austria

Report by Radmila Ustych, FORZA NGO

Date, venue, host, website

14-18/03/2016, Graz, Styria region, Austria

Organized and hosted by HCS and FORZA

This detailed report can be found in Ukrainian language at the FORZA website:

<http://www.forza.org.ua/uk/reram/investiciyi-v-znannya-zavzhdi-dayut-naybilshiy-pributok>

Participants

Ukrainian group – owners and managers of the enterprises:

- Mebli Styl Furniture factory www.hausmobel.eu www.meblistyle.com
- Gelika furniture factory www.gelika.org
- Krokwood Ltd. <http://krokwood.com.ua/en/>
- Eurostandart Ltd. <http://olles.com.ua/>
- Uzhhorod consulting center www.consulting.uz.ua
- Agroderew Ltd. www.agroderew.com
- Interwoodkommerz Ltd.
- WOODWERK factory <http://woodwerk.com/uk/>
- Buk Holding” Ltd. www.bukholding.com.ua

RERAM representatives: HCS (R. Oberwimmer, E. Schmidt), FORZA (L. Loyko, R. Ustych)

The following companies and institutions were visited:

- Katzbeck Fenster www.katzbeck.at/en
- Abalon Hardwood <http://abalon-hardwood.com/>
- Josef Prödl Tischlerei www.proedl.at/en
- EHP European Hardwood Production www.ehp.at/index.php?id=1&L=1
- Weitzer Parkett www.weitzer-parkett.com/en/
- Kulmer Bau www.kulmerbau.at
- Schloffer Furniture Design <http://www.schloffer.com/index.php?id=7>
- KAPO www.kapo.at
- Landwirtschaftliche Fachschule Güssing (Agricultural College) www.lfsguessing.at

Main goal, activities and main outcomes

Learn about set up of wood processing and furniture production in general, with particular focus on efficient use of raw materials and energy.

“An investment in knowledge always pays the best interest”: This quote of Benjamin Franklin, which was pronounced by the director of agricultural college in Güssing, became the theme line of the study tour to wood processing enterprises in Austria.

Day 1

Visit to **Katzbeck Windows** factory was remembered by participants not only because it was the first out of nine enterprises we have visited, but also because of extreme quality of its windows (wood and wood+aluminum), by in-house staff training and by its “green vision”: there are 1800 m² of photovoltaic facility at the roof of the main office, the company rents out e-cars and e-bikes to their staff. As we have understood, success of the company is based on the following pillars:

- High end technology and quality of the highest level
- Reliability, strict compliance with the deadlines, individual approach to clients
- Support of team spirit among the staff

In **Güssing** city we were invited to the exemplary building from wood – training rooms of **agricultural college** and their production premises (cattle and pig barns), made from glued wood. The fact that there are not only residential buildings constructed from wood, but also facilities and commercial building, for us is a novelty (in Austria 15% of all buildings are made from wood), that is why we were interested to examine the buildings. The college director has a very simple, but at the same time, sensible approach towards construction: there is plenty of local resource – wood – around the college, and this resource can and should be used for construction. The building is in line with up to date energy efficiency standards, all premises are accessible for people with special needs. In 2016 new college building has received a special award for buildings from wood.

Next enterprise **Abalon Hardwood GmbH** impressed us by its production capacities – this sawmill with almost complete automatic production is annually processing up to 100 000 m³ of beech timber. Among the advantages the company highlights the following:

The final product is edged, lightly steamed, kiln-dried lumber. Sorting of the products is done after the steaming and kiln-drying and in accordance with the American sorting system (SUPERIOR, CABINET, CUSTOM-SHOP, COMMON-SHOP). This means, that customer buys absolutely predictable timber: no matter what is the purchase date, the customer always gets unified material from the point of view of humidity rate, sort, packaging, steaming colour.

These advantages, seemingly obvious from our viewpoint, produce for the customer a special marketing effect of unique selling point, and favorably distinguish the enterprise from the others.

Day 2

Prödl Carpentry impresses with its organization of production flow. The company produces custom design furniture and it is immediately felt in the atmosphere of the company – less of automatic operations, more of creative and manual work. Design office is the backbone of the company. “Simplicity. Clarity. Quality. This is my philosophy”, - company’s executive Josef Prödl says.

It is interesting that this company is a member of the industrial tourism network. As you go through the production, the special boards depict main approaches of owners towards the production. For example: “There are no compromises when it is about precision and quality”; “We work in accordance with the plan – until the last piece”.

Josef Prödl explained that Prödl Carpentry is more than just furniture, – it is the style of the living space. That is how they position themselves at the market and this is how they are perceived by the customers.

Another sawmill production visited by the group, the **EHP European Hardwood Production**, processes beech, oak and other hardwoods at the annual volume of 45000 m³, out of which 80% are exported. The enterprise purchases raw materials partially from the neighbouring countries (Croatia, Hungary).

Possibilities to purchase products from Ukrainian companies were discussed during **round table**, organized by Wood Cluster Styria and owner of the EHP European Hardwood Production, head of Austrian association of sawmills, Mr. Polz. During this round table participants had a chance to discuss markets, supply and demand for the timber in different parts of the world, as well as issues of possible cooperation between companies.

Day 3

Kulmer constructs wooden buildings, maximum six floors, of residential and commercial purposes (e.g. office of Vienna metropolitan, ski lift station). Here we could see production of light constructions from glued timber (spruce) and special patented elements under the trademark Kielsteg: light and strong construction elements for roof and structural floors with large passes from 5 to 27 m. Kielsteg elements are composed of timber strips, which form top and bottom flanges, connected by curved webs of plywood or OSB.

These elements allow to build cantilever roof elements and use internal space for installment of wires and pipes, at the same time providing aesthetic look of the wooden beam in the interior. Another advantage is the possibility it provides to save costs on the supporting frame and wind bracing in case of the gaps larger than 5 m, because exactly from this point, the use of traditional wooden glued elements becomes not profitable.

The Kielsteg manufacturing process relies on two special machines. The Kielsteg assembly machine made by MINDA is the first of these. This machine produces Kielsteg elements in thicknesses of 228–800 mm and in raw lengths of 17.5–35.0 m. The second machine is the planning machine, which is specially built to handle the wide range of dimensions of the Kielsteg elements. The elements are planned to size in one pass through the machine.

Discussion of the participants, impressed with the scale of wooden structures, because we haven’t seen such product in Ukraine yet, was flowing around possibilities to use these

technologies in Ukraine. All have agreed that, of course, the construction of wooden multi-story apartment buildings or commercial buildings, unfortunately, is not yet a trend in Ukraine, but soon should become a trend and it would be a good niche for those, who will feel the situation and start such production.

Weitzer Parkett Flooring producer of high end parquet, they call their products “intelligent”. All products are produced with special steaming technologies, laser sorting of lamellas, precise geometry. From four sides the plank is preserved from humidity by wax, and the parquet itself is treated with 7 layers of lacquer, which excludes scratches or damage by chemicals. Types of parquet include maintenance-free parquet, “healthy” parquet and “sound-reduction” parquet. Company positions itself as a family company with the responsible attitude towards environment (the production has to be placed in the region and not where it is cheaper, no use of tropical wood) and towards workers. Weitzer Parkett is the company with a long history, run by the 7th generation of owners. Currently the company is managed mostly by women.

KAPO is another furniture producer with focus on contemporary design and durability of the products. During painting and lacquering they use exclusively water-based paints, don't use solvents and don't harm environment. The enterprise is working since 1927 and its success is in the combination of traditions with requirements of contemporary customer. Well thought through idea of the product, use of modern technologies, high quality, often manual work – are the conditions of **KAPO's** success.

Day 4

Schloffer furniture.design produces integrated solutions mainly for foodservice industry. This enterprise designs, produces and installs furniture for clients, like McDonalds all over the world, including Ukraine. In Styria the company produces furniture, besides, in each country the company has network of local partners, which supply elements for decoration, which are carefully selected from the point of view of timely supplies, because average time of starting a McDonalds in a new location is three weeks. Our participants were impressed by the software, which allows to track the whole order and its separate elements from the production decision to the delivery.

From visits to these nine companies we can point out the following common features, which are the basis for effective production:

- Family companies with a long-standing history
- Support of local producers – almost every company buys local raw materials, the products have the sign “Made in Styria”, “Made in Austria”
- Many companies have almost ideal storage of materials, storage operations are automated, efficiency of cutting the material and its use at the parquet and furniture production is close to 100%: the residues from one cutting operation are first priority for use in the next operation
- Boilers use own residues, and its profitability is carefully calculated: at one of the companies we learned that company sells its timber residues at the same time buys

technical timber for its boiler at a 30% lower price. After that all produced electric power is sold into the network at the green tariff and power is bought at the regular price.

- Except for sawmills, all companies work with custom orders. The aim is not to get a long-term contract for large volumes, as everyone understands that today flexibility and individual solutions are the key.

Feedback of participants of the study tour:

- Yuriy Hryha, “Krokwood” Ltd: I was impressed by the fact that Katzbeck company completely documented 113 production processes, and all of them go through continuous optimization process. Exceptional organization of production, no matter how automatic the processes are!
- Anriy Kryshchuk, “Eurostandart” Ltd: companies are completely customer oriented, they talk to client in his language.
- Ihor Khomyk, “Agroderew” Ltd: we have often seen moisturization (water sprayed in the production areas), it improves quality of wood. I noted it down for myself. Where the machine does not work, aspiration closes down, - as a result, energy saving.
- Anatoliy Shamanskyi, “Gelika” furniture factory: we have seen large scale mass production with intensive working dynamics as well as companies with slow rhythm, where there is time for creativity, but we can learn from each of them.
- Volodymyr Turchyn, “Mebli Styl” furniture factory: when I come back home I will make calculations and make a decision whether I go for mass production, or custom orders.
- Yaroslav Rokosovyyk, “Interwoodkommerz”: we should take care of next generations following the experience of Austrian companies.
- Artem Ponomarenko, Woodwerk: Austria is a beautiful country, and its external beauty is a result of mutual respect of all people who live here. Furniture companies are our benchmarks, our reference; it is the visualization of what we dream of.

Study tour participants appreciate deeply the work of Wood Cluster Styria, Mr. Roland Oberwimmer and Mrs. Evelin Schmidt for well-prepared program and excellent organization of the study tour.

3. Annex

3.1 Impressions from the enterprise checks

3.2 Impressions from the SME trainings

3.3 Impressions from the study tour to Austria

3.4 Reality Checks and SME Trainings: Agendas and Participants Lists

confidential; not included in public summary report version

Ukraine

- 3.4.1 Training at K'Len (2 days), 24-25/03/2015, Irshava/ Khust, UA
- 3.4.2 Study Tour for Ukrainian companies to Austria, 14-18/03/2016

Moldova

- 3.4.2 Training at Goliat-Vita (2 days), 04-08/05/2015, Chisinau/ Comrat, MD
- 3.4.3 Training at AITT (1 day), 05/05/2016, Chisinau / Comrat, MD

Georgia

- 3.4.4 Training at Orbeli (3 days), 14-16/04/2015, Tbilisi, GE
- 3.4.5 Training at RECC (2 days), 19-20/04/2016, Tbilisi, GE

Austria

- Note: The Austrian companies received immediate feedback on improvement options during advisory sessions, which were carried out as part of the enterprise check visits.

3.5 Enterprise Reality Check Reports

confidential; not included in public summary report version

- 3.5.1 Reality Check Report Mebli Stil (Ukraine)
- 3.5.2 Reality Check Report K'Len (Ukraine)
- 3.5.3 Reality Check Report Atlant (Ukraine)
- 3.5.4 Reality Check Report Gelika (Ukraine)
- 3.5.5 Reality Check Report Goliat-Vita, Mobilemn, Mob-lumina (Moldova)
- 3.5.6 Reality Check Report Numina (Moldova)
- 3.5.7 Reality Check Report Orbeli (Georgia)
- 3.5.8 Reality Check Report Shno (Georgia)
- 3.5.9 Reality Check Report Golden Hands (Georgia)
- 3.5.10 Reality Check Report Tsunda (Georgia)
- 3.5.11 Reality Check Report Tscheschner (Austria)
- 3.5.12 Reality Check Report Griessner (Austria)
- 3.5.13 Reality Check Report Scheucher (Austria)
- 3.5.14 Reality Check Report Lieco Kalwang (Austria)
- 3.5.15 Reality Check Report Lieco St. Martin (Austria)
- 3.5.16 Reality Check Report Jannach (Austria)
- 3.5.17 Reality Check Report Prödl (Austria)

Notes:

- The companies Goliat-Vita, Mobilemn and Mob-lumina are co-located in the same building complex (joint production facilities). Therefore only one check report was produced.
- For the Caucasus Road Project no reality check report was prepared, because the company operates on a high efficiency level and only very few minor recommendations could be identified (see chapter 2.3.12).
- The Austrian reports are only available in German language.

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Reality check and benchmarking of raw material performance. RERAM public summary report D3.3. Holzcluster Steiermark GmbH, ACECon e.U. - Environmental & Efficiency Consulting, Internationales Institut für Wald und Holz e.V. Graz, Münster. www.reram.eu

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